

Design Of A Legislative Records Management System: A Phased Intervention For The Sangguniang Bayan Of Garchitorena

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Abstract

This study analyzed the current legislative records management practices and challenges and developed a context-specific Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) for the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. The study addressed the persistent reliance on manual and paper-based records management systems, which resulted in delayed document retrieval, limited accessibility, risks of record loss and deterioration, and operational inefficiencies in legislative processes. Grounded in ISO 15489 Records Management Theory, E-Governance Maturity Theory, and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the study utilized Design and Development Research (DDR) Type 1 with a mixed methods approach. Quantitative and qualitative data were gathered from 40 respondents composed of Sangguniang Bayan members, secretariat staff, municipal officials, barangay officials, and stakeholders through survey questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis. Descriptive statistics, weighted mean, standard deviation, and thematic analysis were employed in analyzing the data. Findings revealed that the current legislative records management practices were “Often Practiced” with a domain mean of 4.11, indicating that the system remains functional but highly dependent on manual processes. Respondents also “Strongly Agreed” that the existing manual system posed significant operational challenges with a domain mean of 4.54, particularly in terms of retrieval delays, storage limitations, risks of record damage, and limited accessibility of information. Based on the identified gaps and operational realities of the municipality, the study developed a phased and hybrid Legislative Records Management System integrating manual and digital processes to improve records organization, retrieval, accessibility, transparency, and administrative efficiency. Stakeholders and expert validators generally assessed the proposed intervention as relevant, feasible, and potentially effective for the operational context of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. The study concluded that a phased and context-sensitive LRMS serves as a practical and sustainable intervention for geographically isolated and resource-constrained local government units.

Keywords: *Legislative Records Management, DDR, GIDA, Digital Governance, LGU, Hybrid Systems, E-Government Maturity.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital good governance is critical to transparency, efficiency, and public trust. As emphasized by the World Bank (2021) and the United Nations (2022), the integration of information and communication technologies (ICTs) plays a vital role in modernizing public service delivery. In the Philippines, this ideal is reinforced through mandates from the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) and the Commission on Audit (COA), which require Local Government Units (LGUs) to maintain legislative records that are accessible, accountable, and secure to support informed decision-making.

However, the reality in many Philippine LGUs, particularly in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (GIDA) such as the coastal municipality of Garchitorena, remains far from this vision. In the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena, legislative records management is still anchored in manual, paper-based systems. Legislative documents are stored in physical folders, logbooks, and filing cabinets, often resulting in overcrowded storage conditions and inefficient organization. Instead of a structured and searchable system, the office operates within what can be described as a “maze of paper,” where document retrieval is time-consuming and dependent on staff familiarity with the filing system.

This situation reflects a broader disconnect between national digitalization goals and local implementation capacity. While digital governance frameworks advocate for full ICT integration, these models often assume the presence of adequate infrastructure, financial resources, and technical expertise. As noted by Richard Heeks (2018), many digital initiatives fail due to a mismatch between technological design and local realities, a phenomenon often referred to as the “design–reality gap.” In the case of Garchitorena, limited ICT infrastructure, budget constraints, and geographic isolation make immediate full-scale digital transformation impractical.

The persistence of manual systems leads to significant operational and institutional consequences. Document retrieval becomes a “race against time,” delaying legislative processes and administrative functions. More critically, the municipality’s vulnerability to environmental factors such as humidity, pests, and natural disasters places its legislative records at constant risk of deterioration or loss. The absence of digital backups further exacerbates this risk, threatening the long-term preservation of institutional memory and undermining transparency and accountability in governance.

Despite the growing body of literature on digital governance, existing studies largely focus on general administrative systems and assume resource-rich environments. There is limited empirical research on legislative records management, particularly in the context of resource-constrained LGUs. Moreover, current studies rarely explore phased and adaptive digital interventions suited for GIDA contexts, where incremental and context-sensitive approaches are necessary for successful implementation.

To address these gaps, this study adopts a Design and Development Research (DDR) Type 1 approach to develop a phased Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) tailored

to the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. Unlike conventional models that advocate for immediate and large-scale digital transformation, this study proposes a gradual, hybrid approach grounded in E-Governance Maturity Theory, which emphasizes incremental adoption of digital systems based on institutional readiness.

This study contributes to the literature and practice of public administration in three key ways. First, it provides a context-specific intervention model designed for a GIDA LGU, addressing the gap between global digital governance frameworks and local realities. Second, it demonstrates data-to-design alignment through the use of a Functional Requirement Matrix, ensuring that system features directly respond to identified operational challenges. Third, it advances the concept of phased digitalization frameworks for low-capacity LGUs, offering a practical and scalable pathway for transitioning from manual to digital records management systems.

Ultimately, this research aims to provide a sustainable and realistic solution that enables the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena to gradually transition from manual processes toward an efficient, secure, and accessible legislative records management system.

1.1 Research Objective

This study aims to analyze the current legislative records management practices and challenges, and to develop a context-specific intervention program to enhance records management in the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.

1.2 Specific Objectives

1. To analyze the current legislative records management practices and challenges met by the stakeholders of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.
2. To design a context-specific and phased intervention program to enhance the legislative records management practices in the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.
3. To describe the stakeholders' acceptability of the designed intervention program.
4. To propose strategies and recommendations for the implementation of a Legislative Records Management System.

1.3 Scope and Delimitation

Designing a context-specific and phase-by-phase Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) as an intervention program is the focus of this study based on the analysis of the current records management, particularly on the organization, storage, and retrieval, and accessibility of legislative documents such as ordinances and resolutions, and records of the session in the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena, Camarines Sur. This phase-by-phase, or adaptive, approach is more appropriate than a full-blown digital transformation, given the LGU's

identified gaps and operational conditions. Also, the acceptability of the proposed intervention program to stakeholders is considered, in terms of relevance, feasibility, and potential usefulness.

The unit of analysis of the study is the Sangguniang Bayan members, the SB secretariat staff, selected municipal officials, and the stakeholders who access the legislative records. Their responses are how their current practices were analyzed, the challenges identified, and how the proposed LRMS was accepted. The study is delimited to the design and validation of the proposed LRMS, not its actual implementation or system testing.

1.4 Limitations of the Study

This study is subject to the following limitations. First, the researchers limited scope focuses only on the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena, thereby limiting the generalizability of the findings to other Local Government Units with differing institutional capacities and resources. Second, the study relied on respondents' self-reports, which were subjective and did not fully capture everything in operation. Finally, the proposed intervention program is limited to the design and expert validation phase, which aligns with Design and Development Research (DDR) Type 1. The study did not cover the actual implementation or measure the system's performance.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

Figure 1.

Theoretical Framework Paradigm

As shown in Figure 1, the study integrates Records Management Theory (ISO 15489), E-Governance Maturity Theory, and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Together, these frameworks provide a foundation for analyzing current practices, designing a graduated intervention, and evaluating stakeholder buy-in.

As the primary foundation, ISO 15489 (2001) dictates the systematic control of records throughout their lifecycle—from creation and classification to storage and disposal. This theory provides the metrics for evaluating the Sangguniang Bayan's existing manual system and identifying critical gaps in reliability and accessibility. It justifies the need for a structured

standardization, digitization, and structured retrieval. This variable is adaptive, meaning its design is directly moderated by the constraints and gaps identified in the independent variables.

The dependent variable is the Stakeholder Acceptability of the LRMS, evaluated through the lenses of relevance, feasibility, and potential effectiveness. This represents the final validation stage of the study. The level of acceptability determines the outcome: a set of Implementation Strategies—including capacity-building and phased adoption—that ensure the system is not only technologically sound but also institutionally sustainable within the Garchitorena context.

1. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Design

The study employs Design and Development Research (DDR) Type 1, which focuses on the systematic design and validation of an intervention artifact without full implementation. This approach is appropriate for addressing real-world administrative inefficiencies through context-sensitive system development.

2.2. Research Strategy

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, wherein quantitative data collection and analysis were conducted in the initial phase, followed by qualitative data collection to further explain and contextualize the quantitative results.

In Phase 1 (quantitative), survey data were gathered from respondents to assess the current legislative records management practices, identify operational challenges, and determine the level of acceptability of the proposed intervention. Statistical analysis, including weighted mean and standard deviation, was used to establish patterns and trends in the data.

In Phase 2 (qualitative), Key Informant Interviews (KII) and document analysis were conducted to provide deeper insights into the quantitative findings. This phase aimed to explain the underlying reasons behind the observed patterns, such as delays in document retrieval, inconsistencies in filing practices, and limitations in storage and accessibility. The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of recurring themes that complemented and enriched the quantitative results.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings enabled a comprehensive understanding of the research problem by combining measurement with contextual explanation. This approach ensured methodological rigor through triangulation, enhancing the validity and reliability of the study by corroborating results across multiple data sources.

2.3. Participants

A total of 40 respondents participated in the study, selected using a combination of purposive and convenience sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was employed to ensure that participants had direct involvement in legislative records management processes, while convenience sampling was utilized due to accessibility constraints and the limited number of personnel within the municipality.

The respondents consisted of key stakeholders involved in the creation, management, and utilization of legislative records, including Sangguniang Bayan members, Secretariat staff, selected municipal officials, and records users such as municipal employees and barangay stakeholders. This composition ensured representation from both the legislative and administrative perspectives, as well as end-users of legislative records.

The selected participants were considered appropriate for the study as they possess firsthand knowledge and experience in records management practices within the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. Their involvement provided relevant insights into current operational challenges and informed the design and evaluation of the proposed Legislative Records Management System (LRMS).

2.4. Data Collection

Data were collected using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure a comprehensive analysis of legislative records management practices. A structured survey questionnaire utilizing a five-point Likert scale was administered to respondents to assess current practices, identify challenges, and evaluate the acceptability of the proposed Legislative Records Management System (LRMS).

To complement the survey data, Key Informant Interviews (KII) were conducted with selected participants who have direct involvement in legislative records management. These interviews provided in-depth insights into operational issues, contextual constraints, and practical experiences that could not be fully captured through quantitative measures.

In addition, a document analysis checklist was employed to examine existing legislative records, filing systems, and documentation practices within the Sangguniang Bayan. This method enabled the verification of reported practices and supported the triangulation of findings across multiple data sources.

2.5. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques consistent with the explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. Quantitative data from the survey were analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviation to determine the level of current practices, challenges, and acceptability of the

proposed phased Legislative Records Management System (LRMS). Descriptive statistics were used to identify patterns and trends in respondents' perceptions.

Qualitative data obtained from Key Informant Interviews (KII) and document analysis were analyzed using thematic analysis, following the approach of Braun and Clarke. Responses were transcribed, coded, and organized into recurring themes that explain and contextualize the quantitative findings.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative results was achieved through triangulation and meta-inference, allowing for a comprehensive interpretation of the data. This approach ensured that numerical results were supported and explained by qualitative evidence, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the study.

2.6. Design Logic

The study followed a data-to-design logic consistent with Design and Development Research (DDR) principles, ensuring that the proposed phased Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) was empirically grounded and contextually appropriate. The process began with the identification of problems through the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings, including survey results, Key Informant Interviews (KII), and document analysis. These findings provided a comprehensive understanding of existing practices and operational challenges in legislative records management.

Subsequently, the identified problems were translated into specific system features and functional requirements through the development of a Functional Requirement Matrix, which mapped operational needs to corresponding technological and procedural solutions. This ensured that the system design directly addressed the issues experienced by stakeholders.

The proposed phased LRMS was then subjected to validation through stakeholder evaluation and expert review to assess its relevance, feasibility, and appropriateness within the local government context. Feedback from these evaluations informed the refinement of the system design, ensuring alignment with institutional capacity, resource availability, and operational requirements.

Overall, this iterative process ensured strong data–design alignment, allowing the proposed LRMS to serve as a practical and sustainable intervention tailored to the needs of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.

2. RESULTS

3.1. Current Practices

Table 1 presents the respondents' assessment of the current legislative records management practices in the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.

Table 1.

Current Legislative Records Management Practices Assessment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Std Dev	Qualitative Evidence (KII/Documentation)	Meta-Inference	Type
Legislative records are stored primarily in physical/manual format	4.20	Always Practiced	0.65	Manually filed and not archived electronically as evidenced by KII responses and lack of electronic filing/checklist process	Systems still heavily dependent on manual process resulting in inefficiencies and increasing "risk of loss" of legislative record	Confirmation
Retrieving documents from the manual system takes significant time	3.80	Often Practiced	1.05	Staff reports experiencing delays on locating documents during interviews	The amount of time estimating delays would also be very significant due to the number of legislative workflow processing and document processing impacted by manual retrieval systems	Confirmation
The current manual filing system is organized and easy to follow	4.00	Often Practiced	0.65	Some documents ordered chronologically yet do not have indices	As such, the current manual filing systems have limited overall organization and are lacking standard operating procedures (i.e., indexing) to make them more efficient	Expansion
Files are sometimes misplaced or difficult to locate	3.90	Often Practiced	1.04	Document shows impairment to respondent locating files during interviews	Lack of standardization in processing and indexing of documents to retrieve them decreases the accessibility/credibility of legislative records	Confirmation
Manual processes slow down work flow	4.40	Always Practiced	0.74	Respondents noted legislative processing has taken longer than it would if the processes were more efficient and independent of the manual process or system.	Manual processes create significant operational inefficiencies and impediments to performing legislative functions	Enhancement
Domain Mean	4.11		0.83	-	The current system is functional but inefficient and unreliable	Enhancement

Note: Quantitative evidence derived from KII and document analysis.

Legend for Mean:

4.50 - 5.00 Always practiced

3.50 - 4.49 Often practiced

2.50 - 3.49 Sometimes practiced

1.50 - 2.49 Rarely practiced

1.00 - 1.49 Never practiced

The overall evaluation of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena's records management of legislative documents resulted in a mean of 4.11 which was interpreted as "Often Practiced", meaning that records management activities in general are being regularly carried out, and personnel do things about filing, storage, and document retrieval of legislative documents/activities. This also suggests that while it is functional, it may not yet fully optimized in terms of efficiency, accessibility, and standardization.

Findings reveal that records of legislative proceedings are predominantly stored in physical or manual form (Mean = 4.20), and that processes that are done manually do slow down workflow considerably (Mean = 4.40). These affirm the dependency on records management practices that, though "friendly" to people of the Sangguniang Bayan, still hampers the quickness and promptness of legislative work. This may also mean that although the Sangguniang Bayan can thrive through managing its records, the lack of computer applications limits its ability to give timely and prompt services.

However, the least positively rated coindicator was the time to retrieve documents from the manual system (Mean = 3.80), indicating that document retrieval is a problem and that records are kept, but they are not quickly retrieved if they are needed for something. This is likely due to the fact that there are no indexes, everything is filed differently, and in fact, things are possibly just filed chronologically, and not by any system method.

Examining these indicators individually it is apparent that while the filing system is perceived as somewhat organized (Mean = 4.00), it is yet to have a standard and indexing system, which is important for good records management. A similar concern relates to misplaced or hard to find files (Mean = 3.90) which again indicates that there is no clear filing system in place.

Evidence from the interview process was also consistent with those discussed in (B. E. Asogwa, 2019), suggesting that paper-based manual records management systems in government offices are synonymous with inefficiency, difficulty in information retrieval and limited access to information. Systems that are not modernized lead to procrastination in information processing, and staff and organizational performance will be impaired. In line with these results, this study also found that an over-reliance on manual systems exerts a negative impact on records management efforts.

Additional obstacles arise from settings where there is little or no ICT infrastructure, where there are no established records management policies, and where government capacity is so constrained that personnel may not have access to the technical capabilities in the Department of Information and Communications Technology in the Philippines. For poorer municipalities such as Garchitorena, where the level of technology access may also be absent, the move to digital becomes harder.

Based on the foregoing results, it was concluded that even if the legislative records management practices of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena are regularly implemented, they are still inefficient, unstandardized, and heavily reliant on manual means. We recommend that this office develop and institutionalize standardized procedures in filing, develop a classification and indexing system, and slowly adopt minimum viable digital tools such as document scanning and electronic databases. A phased, context-specific approach in upgrading their office will go a long way in improving the sustainability of practices while also improving efficiency, accessibility, and performance in records management.

3.2. Challenges

Table 2 outlines the problems faced with the manual records management system for the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena legislators.

Table 2.

Challenges in Manual Legislative Records Management

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	StdDev	Qualitative Evidence / (KII/Document Analysis)	Meta-Inference	Type
Manual system consumes too much storage space	4.44	Strongly Agree	0.75	Document Checklist shows limited storage space	Records Management is limited by storage space	Confirmation
Risks of loss / damage of records	4.51	Strongly Agree	0.58	No fireproof cabinets; exposure to environment	Records can easily be lost, damaged, or placed at risk due to the environment.	Enhancement
Retrieval delays that affect legislative process	4.48	Strongly Agree	0.62	Interviews confirm workflow disruption	Legislative workflow is disrupted by delayed retrieval of records and delays in service delivery due to lack of methodology.	Enhancement
Staff have trouble in managing large volume of records	4.57	Strongly Agree	0.61	Staff reported difficulty handling files	The current system does not scale effectively to cope with increased numbers of records.	Confirmation
Limited access to information for a decision making	4.71	Strongly Agree	0.54	Respondents noted delays in decision-making	The limited availability of records affects decision making processes.	Enhancement
Domain Mean	4.54	Strongly Agree	0.62		Problems are deep-rooted and broad-based.	Enhancement

Note: Qualitative evidence is derived from Key Informant Interviews (KII) and document analysis.

Legend for Mean:

4.50 - 5.00 Strongly Agree

3.50 - 4.49 Agree

2.50 - 3.49 Neutral

1.50 - 2.49 Disagree

1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

The challenges experienced in the manual legislative records management system are presented in Table 2. The result shows a domain mean of 4.54 which is interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. This indicates that Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena would strongly experience challenges in the manual records management system. This indicates that records management is being carried out, however, the system is overloaded and cannot meet the current demands being placed on it.

Majority of the respondents agreed that lack of information for decision making (Mean = 4.71) was very severe, followed by large number of records difficult to manage (Mean = 4.57) and risk of loss of records (Mean = 4.51). Apart from some vegetable dangers, what these results also hide are institutional constraints related to legislative decision making. It shows how manual system restrict prompt access to information and custody of records, as well as how the quality of records information system is directly related to how timely decisions can be made in the Legislative Assembly itself.

Even the lowest-rated indicator, manual system consumes too much storage space (Mean = 4.44), falls under “Strongly Agree.” This means that all of the identified challenges are experienced consistently and with a significant intensity. This underscores that the challenges are systemic and associated with several issues including storage, retrieval, access and preservation.

Examining the indicators, one can infer that the storage capacity and growing amount of records limit the ability of the office to keep materials organized and accessible. Lack of space, computer backups and fire proof cabinets compound the problem. Also, the delays in retrieval (Mean = 4.48) interrupts the workings of the legislature itself. Without the ability to quickly access, work on, and finalize documents, the process of review and decision-making falters. The risk or loss or damage is great also because there is no appropriate storage such as fire proof cabinets, and environmental controls.

These findings corroborate the results of B. E. Asogwa (2019) and Patrick Ngulube (2022), who stated that a manual records room and records management systems are characterized with inefficiency, proneness to loss and damage, and limitations in scale. The authors suggest that emphasizing manual processes in resource-constrained environments gives rise to inefficiencies, delays, and risks that undermine organizational performance and service delivery.

These problems can arise when sufficient ICT infrastructure is not in place, there are no records management policies in place and no investment is made into proper records management systems. In the case of Garchitorena, these problems are exacerbated by geographical and resource limitations that prevent any form of migration from paper to digital system.

From the results, it is reasonable to deduce that the manual system of records management on legislative enactments of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena is far

from adequate in today's climate of good governance. There is no simple solution to the problems identified earlier in this chapter as they are deep, endemic, and mutually compounding - leading to the need for a properly conceived and a carefully planned approach to solving these problems.

For that reason, we must recommend that the Sangguniang Bayan adopt a gradual, context-based LRMS that favours digitized records as well as standardizing records processes, as well as improving storage and retrieval while keeping in mind the painfully slow and torturous way that things currently are and coaxing accessibility, security and the minor administrative experience out of it.

3.3. Functional Requirement Matrix

Table 3.

Functional Requirement Matrix for the Proposed Phased Legislative Records Management System

Identified Problem (Empirical Findings)	Root Cause (Qualitative Insight)	System Requirement / Feature	Description of Feature	Expected Output
Slow Retrieval	Lack of indexing system	Digital Indexing System	Assigns searchable metadata (date, title, ordinance no.)	Fast document retrieval
Overcrowded storage space	Purely physical filing system	Hybrid Storage System	Combines physical and digital storage such as scanned copies	Reduced the storage burden
The risk of loss or damage of records	No backup	Digital Backup & Archiving	Stores scanned records in external/digital storage	Reduced physical storage requirements
Inconsistent filing practices	No standard classification	Standardized Filing Protocol	Establishes uniform classification and labelling system	Organized records management
Delays in legislative workflow	Manual processing	Document Tracking System	Tracks document movement and status	Improved workflow efficiency.
Limited access to the information	Only physical access	Controlled Digital Access	Provides access via local computer system	Increased accessibility
Low ICT capacity	Limited to digital literacy	Phased Implementation Design	Gradual transition (manual to hybrid to digital)	Feasible system adoption

Note: The Established Problem Statement to Functional Requirements will ensure the database design will align with data requirements for system functions and output.

The following is the Functional Requirement Matrix of the proposed phased Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) for the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. Table 3 presents the Functional Requirement Matrix developed for the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. It maps the identified problems in legislative records management with the proposed features of the proposed system and the expected outputs.

By approaching major operational issues—retrieving documents is often difficult; no standardized filing is available; storage is insufficient; and less accessible in managing files—with key features such as digital index, classification, workflow tracking, and controlled access, it is clear to see that this proposed Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) is not arbitrary and is rather data-driven and needs-based, making sure that every component of the system respond to challenges actually experienced within the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. This approach is congruent with Design and Development Research (DDR) principles that a system's design must be based on

empirical findings, to be aligned with user needs to be effective and usable (Peffer, et al., 2007); and records management best practices that a problem must always be aligned to a structured solution by system.

It is recommended therefore that the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena be guided by the Functional Requirement Matrix for the system's implementation of the LRMS and ensure that all the features of the system is aligned with the identified operational needs and always updated as needed in the event of the emergence of new requirements during system adoption.

Although the study identified significant constraints such as limited infrastructure, storage challenges, and low digital readiness, these findings do not negate the need for system improvement. Instead, they highlight the necessity for a phased and adaptive intervention. The high level of stakeholder acceptability suggests that personnel recognize the limitations of the current manual system and are open to gradual improvements. Thus, the proposed Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) is designed not as an immediate full digital transformation, but as a hybrid and incremental solution that begins with process standardization and basic digital support, eventually progressing toward more advanced functionalities as institutional capacity improves.

Phase Structure of the Proposed Legislative Records Management System

1st Phase: Structure of the New Legislative Records Management System, Records Standardization & Organization (Foundational Stage) This stage relates to improving on the existing manual system by standardizing filing procedures, classifying systems of how records are stored, and creating an indexing mechanism of how records are stored as well as how custodians of records will be described and developed for the purpose of being able to improve access to the records to find them in the system.

2nd Phase: Basic Digitization (Transitional Stage) During this phase, the first step in basic digital support will occur, consisting of scanning high-priority legislative documents into a simple database system and establishing a simple digital storage and backup procedure to enhance record preservation.

3rd Phase: The Digital Retrieval & Management System (Enhancement Phase) During this phase of the project, the goal will be to create a basic search & retrieval system and database for users to have access to records through established user authentication controls and retrieval procedures.

4th Phase: An Indeterminate Stage: During this stage, there will be ongoing gradual improvements to the components of the digital legislative records management system and ongoing training of all users will take place to institutionalize policies in conjunction with monitoring and evaluating their effectiveness, as well as improving the information & communication technology (ICT) resources used by the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena; through continued Investment in this area at all levels (local, state, national levels).

3.4. Acceptability of Phased LRMS

The objective of this chapter is to discuss the level of acceptability, or lack thereof, of the proposed phase-in Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) among the stakeholders of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.

Table 4.

Acceptability of the Intervention Program.

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	StdDev	Qualitative Evidence / (KII/Document Analysis)	Meta-Interference	Type
Relevant to Needs	4.63	Strongly Acceptable	0.55	Respondents expressed need for faster access	The intervention strongly aligns with the operational needs of the LGU.	Confirmation
Feasible	4.31	Strongly Acceptable	0.68	KII shows needs for a training and support	Implementation is feasible but dependent on available resources and support systems.	Expansion
Improves Workflow	4.56	Strongly Acceptable	0.60	Respondents highlighted reduction of delays and faster processing	The intervention can significantly enhance workflow efficiency and processing speed	Enhancement
Easy to Implement	4.44	Strongly Acceptable	0.66	Staff staff expressed willingness but emphasized need training	Implementation is acceptable with appropriate capacity-building measures	Expansion
Support better Records Management	4.59	Strongly Acceptable	0.58	Document Analysis shows need for structure system	The intervention strengthens system organization and records management practices	Confirmation
Domain Mean	4.51	Strongly Acceptable	0.61	-	Intervention program is highly acceptable and suitable for implementation	Enhancement

Note: Qualitative evidence is derived from Key Informant Interviews (KII) and document analysis.

Legend for Mean:

4.50 – 5.00 Strongly Acceptable

3.50 – 4.49 Slightly Acceptable

2.50 – 3.49 Acceptable

1.50 – 2.49 Least Acceptable

1.00 – 1.49 Not Acceptable

This part shows the level of acceptability of the proposed phased LRMS to the stakeholders of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. Helper Table 6 shows a domain mean of 4.51 which is interpreted as “Strongly Acceptable”. This connotes that the stakeholders had highly accepted the proposed intervention program, indicating that the proposed LRMS was judged by the respondents as relevant, useful and appropriate in addressing the existing records management issues.

The study revealed that respondents considered, the intervention is relevant to organizational needs (Mean = 4.63), it enhances records management (Mean = 4.59), and it enhances workflow (Mean = 4.56). This denotes how well the stakeholders understood that the system can help improve their operational performance in terms of its use in making documents readily-available, making it delays-free, and assisting them in organizing records, it can be assumed that the proposed LRMS is very close to the actual needs of the Sangguniang Bayan.

However, even the lowest ranked indicator, feasibility (Mean = 4.31), although falling within the upper bounds of “Strongly Acceptable,” still demonstrates that stakeholders have concerns regarding whether they would have sufficient resources, technical capacity, and system support to utilize a digital health technology effectively. Likewise, the indicator ease of implementation (Mean = 4.44) indicates that while the system is acceptable, stakeholders feel that training and institutional support need to be provided for successful adoption.

From the foregoing analysis one can conclude that stakeholders; are willing to accept it only if the proposed system would promote capacity-building, technical guidance and availability of resources. From this finding it would seem that acceptability depends not on perceptions only but also on the conditions to enable one to use it.

The results are consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model developed by Fred Davis (1989) which states that the users' system acceptance is determined to a large extent by their perceptions of the usefulness of the system and perceived ease of use. The high acceptance ratings reflect the strong perceived usefulness since one of the concerns on feasibility and implementation focuses on perceived ease of use and facilitating conditions.

Furthermore, the high acceptability scores reflect stakeholders' awareness of current system shortcomings and openness to innovation and system enhancement, provided proper change management strategies are put in place.

With this finding, we conclude the proposed LRMS is acceptable, appropriate and beneficial to the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena but the success of its acceptance will depend on how the issues on training, technical assistance and resource person allocation are solved.

We therefore strongly urge the Sanggunian Bayan to extend a phased implementation of the LRMS with focus on capacity building program, technical and ICT resource assistance for the successful acceptance and sustained utilization of the system.

3.4. Expert Validation

Table 5.

Expert Validation Results of the Proposed Phased LRMS.

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	StdDev	Qualitative Evidence / (KII/Document Analysis)	Meta-Interference	Type
Clarity of Design	5.00	Very Highly Acceptable	0.55	The phases of the LRMS are clear, logically ordered, and simple for the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena to understand as they operate within their environment, according to the opinions of the experts.	The system design is clearly structured, and user-friendly for the LGU.	Enhancement
Relevance to the LGU Needs	4.44	Very Highly Acceptable	0.50	All of the validators said that the identified LRMS will assist the Sangguniang Bayan with some of the current challenges in retrieving, storing and accessing records that are common to all LGUs.	The system effectively addresses operational needs.	Confirmation
Feasibility of the Implementation	4.56	Very Highly Acceptable	0.51	According to the experts, the phased method for implementing the LRMS system will make the system real and possible, given the present LGU resources and conditions.	The system is feasible within existing institutional capacity.	Enhancement
Completeness of Components	4.78	Very Highly Acceptable	0.42	While validators did recognize that the LRMS includes critical requirements for records management: classifying records, storing and retrieving records and monitoring records, there continues to be a need for ongoing training and support of staff members implementing records management processes.	The system includes comprehensive and essential components.	Expansion
Alignment with LGU Capacity	4.44	Very Highly Acceptable	0.50	Experts noted that the design of LRMS is very flexible and realistic for an LGU with limited resources, allowing for implementation of the records management system based on available human capital, time, and financial resources.	The system aligns with the technical, financial, and human resource capacity of the LGU.	Enhancement
Domain Mean	4.64	Very Highly Acceptable	0.39	The expert evaluations demonstrate a high level of agreement regarding the viability, usability, and applicability of the LRMS system to the context of LGUs.	The proposed LRMS is highly valid, acceptable, and ready for phased implementation in the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena.	Enhancement

Note: Qualitative evidence is based on expert validators' evaluation and professional judgment.

Legend for Mean:

- 4.50 – 5.00 Always practiced
- 3.50 – 4.49 Often practiced
- 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes practiced
- 1.50 – 2.49 Rarely practiced
- 1.00 – 1.49 Never practiced

This section presents the expert validation of the phased LRMS proposed for the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. Based on the results in table 5, the domain mean of 4.64 is interpreted as “Very Highly Acceptable,” which means that the expert validators strongly agree on the overall quality, relevance, feasibility, and appropriateness of the proposed system for implementation by the local government.

The clarity of design garnered the highest mean score (Mean = 5.00), followed by the completeness of components (Mean = 4.78) and feasibility of implementation (Mean = 4.56). This suggested that these factors indicate that the system is well-structured, logically sequenced, and comprehensive, with clearly defined phases that is easy to grasp and applicable machine used in the operational context of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. This suggests that the LRMS design incorporates all essential records management processes like classification, storage, retrieval, and monitoring.

However, the indicators relevance to LGUs needs (Mean = 4.44) and indicator alignment with LGUs capacity (Mean = 4.44), also interpreted as “Very Highly Acceptable,” suggest that experts recognize the need of aligning with institutional capacity, available resources, and governance structures, which suggests that although highly appropriate, for the system to last it also needs to have the institutional support and enablement to do so.

These findings are consistent with the notions of Design and Development Research (DDR), especially as stressed by Peffers et al. (2007), who highlight the need for expert validation in evaluating system usability, feasibility and readiness for implementation. In our case, expert feedback further exacerbates our LRMS to make it both empirically-grounded and context-aware.

The study concludes that the proposed phased LRMS is indeed valid, acceptable, and implementable, although it still requires policy support, infrastructure readiness, technical maintenance, and both informal and formal capacity-building measures for it to work effectively in the long run.

Thus, it is recommended that the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena adopt the LRMS through a phased implementation approach, supported by:

- Immediate policy institutionalization of records management practices
- Capacity-building and training programs for personnel
- Provision of ICT infrastructure, particularly internet connectivity
- Allocation of additional manpower for system operations
- Development of a system enhancement roadmap and documentation
- Continuous monitoring and evaluation mechanisms

to ensure sustainability, adaptability, and improved legislative performance.

3. DISCUSSIONS

The findings of this study reinforce the argument that manual records management systems in public institutions are inherently inefficient and unsustainable, particularly in resource-constrained environments such as geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (GIDA). Although the results indicate that current practices are regularly implemented, the dominance of manual processes significantly limits retrieval speed, accessibility, and data reliability. In line with ISO 15489, the absence of standardized classification, indexing, and retention mechanisms undermines the integrity and usability of records, thereby affecting the overall efficiency of legislative operations. This supports existing literature which emphasizes that poorly structured records systems contribute to delays, information loss, and weakened institutional accountability.

Furthermore, the study provides empirical support for E-Governance Maturity Theory, demonstrating that phased digitalization is more appropriate than immediate full-scale transformation in low-capacity LGUs. Rather than adopting a disruptive “big bang” approach to digital transformation, the proposed Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) follows a gradual, adaptive progression—from manual standardization to basic digitization and eventually to a digital retrieval system. This phased approach acknowledges institutional limitations in infrastructure, technical capacity, and financial resources, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful adoption and long-term sustainability.

From a behavioral and organizational perspective, the high acceptability ratings of the proposed LRMS further validate the relevance of the Technology Acceptance Model. The findings suggest that stakeholders perceive the system as both useful and feasible, which are key determinants of technology adoption. However, qualitative evidence also highlights concerns regarding training, technical support, and resource availability, indicating that perceived ease of use is contingent upon adequate capacity-building measures. This underscores the importance of complementing technological interventions with organizational support systems to ensure effective implementation.

Importantly, this study advances the concept of adaptive digital governance, particularly in addressing the “last-mile problem” in ICT implementation. Traditional digital governance models often assume uniform conditions across institutions, leading to implementation gaps when applied to low-resource contexts. In contrast, the proposed LRMS is designed to align with the specific institutional realities of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena, including its GIDA classification, limited ICT infrastructure, and reliance on manual processes. By embedding flexibility, scalability, and context sensitivity into the system design, the study demonstrates that effective digital transformation must be locally grounded rather than universally imposed.

Moreover, the use of a Functional Requirement Matrix highlights the importance of data–design alignment in system development. By directly linking identified problems to system features and expected outputs, the study ensures that the LRMS is not merely theoretical but responsive to actual operational needs. This approach strengthens the practical contribution of

the research and aligns with Design and Development Research (DDR) principles, which emphasize iterative design, validation, and refinement based on empirical evidence.

Overall, the findings suggest that improving legislative records management in LGUs requires not only technological innovation but also institutional readiness, policy support, and capacity development. The proposed phased LRMS provides a viable pathway for transitioning from manual to digital systems while minimizing disruption and maximizing sustainability in resource-constrained environments.

4. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that legislative records management in geographically isolated and disadvantaged area (GIDA) local government units is significantly constrained by systemic inefficiencies inherent in manual, paper-based systems. While existing practices remain functional, they are characterized by slow document retrieval, limited accessibility, vulnerability to loss or damage, and a lack of standardization, all of which hinder efficient legislative operations and informed decision-making.

In response to these challenges, the proposed phased Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) offers a contextually grounded, scalable, and sustainable intervention. By adopting a gradual transition from manual to digital processes, the system aligns with the institutional capacity, resource availability, and operational realities of the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorena. This phased approach ensures that digital transformation is both feasible and adaptable, minimizing disruption while enhancing efficiency, accessibility, and data security.

Moreover, the integration of Design and Development Research (DDR), explanatory sequential mixed-methods analysis, and a Functional Requirement Matrix demonstrates a strong data–design alignment, ensuring that the system is directly informed by empirical findings and stakeholder needs. This methodological approach strengthens the validity and practical relevance of the proposed intervention.

Beyond the immediate context, the study contributes to the broader field of digital governance by offering a replicable and adaptable model for similar LGUs facing infrastructure and capacity limitations. It highlights the importance of designing technology-driven interventions that are not only theoretically sound but also responsive to local conditions, thereby addressing the persistent gap between digital governance ideals and implementation realities in resource-constrained environments.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several strategic recommendations are proposed to support the effective implementation and sustainability of the Legislative Records Management System (LRMS) in the Sangguniang Bayan of Garchitorea and similar local government units.

First, it is recommended that the LGU adopt a phased implementation strategy for the LRMS. A gradual transition from manual to digital processes will allow the organization to align system adoption with available resources, minimize operational disruptions, and build institutional readiness over time. This approach is particularly critical in GIDA contexts where immediate full-scale digitalization may not be feasible.

Second, the LGU should institutionalize records management policies at the early stages of implementation. Establishing clear guidelines on classification, storage, retrieval, access control, and retention will ensure consistency and sustainability of records management practices. These policies should be formally integrated into the operations of the Sangguniang Bayan to ensure continuity even with changes in leadership or personnel.

Third, there is a need to invest in capacity-building and ICT infrastructure. Training programs should be conducted to enhance the technical competencies of personnel, particularly in digital records management and system utilization. At the same time, improvements in ICT infrastructure—such as reliable internet connectivity, hardware, and data storage systems—are essential to support the functionality of the LRMS.

Fourth, the LGU should establish mechanisms for continuous monitoring and evaluation of the system. Regular assessment of system performance, user satisfaction, and operational outcomes will enable timely identification of issues and facilitate necessary adjustments. This ensures that the LRMS remains responsive to evolving organizational needs.

Finally, it is recommended to develop context-sensitive digital governance frameworks for GIDA LGUs. Policymakers and practitioners should recognize that digital transformation strategies must be adapted to local conditions rather than adopting one-size-fits-all solutions. The phased LRMS model proposed in this study may serve as a reference for designing similar interventions in other resource-constrained municipalities.

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